

Educational Support by Grandparents and Human Capital Growth: An OLG Model with Endogenous Time Allocation

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Abstract: This study explores the role of grandparents in the education of their grandchildren within an overlapping generations model. We introduce an endogenously determined time allocation, where grandparents decide how much time to dedicate to their grandchildren's education based on a trade-off between leisure and educational contributions. The model shows that grandparental involvement in education influences the intergenerational transmission of human capital, with the potential for long-term effects on economic outcomes. By combining theoretical analysis and simulations, we highlight the dynamic relationship between grandparental education, human capital development, and the generational transmission process.

Keywords: OVERLAPPING GENERATIONS MODELS, ENDOGENOUS TIME ALLOCATION, EDUCATIONAL SUPPORT, FAMILY ECONOMICS, DYNAMICAL SYSTEMS

1. Introduction

The increasing longevity of the population has led to significant changes in family dynamics, especially regarding the role of grandparents in the education of their grandchildren. As life expectancy rises, grandparents are increasingly able to form extended relationships with their grandchildren, providing more opportunities to influence their educational outcomes. This paper explores the role of grandparents in the intergenerational transmission of human capital, focusing on the endogeneity of the time that grandparents dedicate to their grandchildren's education. Unlike in Baldi et al. [1], where this time was considered a fixed portion, in the present work we treat it as a variable determined by the trade-off between leisure and the desire to contribute to grandchildren's upbringing. In our overlapping generations model, we examine how the time grandparents invest in education, along with their own human capital, affects the educational outcomes of younger generations. Our findings suggest that grandparental involvement significantly shapes the human capital of grandchildren, influencing their cognitive development and academic achievements. This model provides new insights into how such intergenerational contributions might affect the transmission of education over time, ultimately impacting long-term social and economic outcomes [2, 3].

This article is structured as follows: in section 2, we introduce the model along with the tools used for its solution. Section 3 presents the solution of the model. Section 4 provides a discussion of the results, both from a theoretical and analytical perspective. Finally, we conclude in section 5.

2. Prerequisites and means for solving the problem

We analyze an Overlapping Generations (OLG) model where agents live for three periods: childhood, adulthood, and old age. In each period, agents make decisions related to consumption, time allocation, and child-rearing, with special attention to the role of grandparents in the education of grandchildren.

The economy at time t consists of three types of agents: the old (N_{t-1}), the adults (N_t), and the young (N_{t+1}), with the number of young agents evolving according to the number of children per adult, n_t , at time t . Specifically, the population evolves as:

$$N_{t+1} = n_t N_t. \tag{1}$$

Adults allocate their time between work and child-rearing, with a special focus on the educational role played by grandparents. In retirement, the elderly divide their time between leisure and educating grandchildren. This model highlights how this time allocation, particularly the time spent educating grandchildren, is influenced by the level of human capital, denoted by h_t , which is dependent on the educational investments of both parents and grandparents.

At time t , an adult maximizes utility from various factors: consumption during adulthood and old age, the number of children, the human capital of children, leisure time, and the time spent educating grandchildren. The adult's utility function U_t is given by:

$$\ln c_{1,t} + \rho \ln c_{2,t+1} + \theta \ln l_{t+1} + \frac{h_t}{h_{t-1}} \ln \mu_{t+1} + \beta \ln h_{t+1} + \lambda \ln n_t, \tag{2}$$

where:

- ❖ $c_{1,t} > 0$ represents consumption during adulthood,
- ❖ $c_{2,t+1} > 0$ represents consumption during old age,
- ❖ $n_t > 0$ is the number of children,
- ❖ $h_{t+1} > 0$ is the human capital of the offspring,
- ❖ $\mu_{t+1} \in (0, 1)$ represents the time fraction devoted to educating grandchildren during retirement,
- ❖ $l_{t+1} \in (0, 1)$ represents the time fraction devoted to leisure during retirement,
- ❖ $\rho \in (0, 1)$ represents the discount factor, reflecting the preference for future consumption over present consumption,
- ❖ $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ reflects the preference for the number of children, capturing the desire for larger family size,
- ❖ $\beta \in (0, 1)$ denotes the weight placed on child quality, as measured by the human capital of the next generation,
- ❖ $\theta > 0$ indicates the value placed on leisure time in old age.

Moreover, $\frac{h_t}{h_{t-1}}$ in (2) reflects human capital growth between generations.

The model also incorporates the cost of child-rearing and education into the budget constraints. Specifically, adults' available income at time t , determined by their wage rate $w_t > 0$ and human capital level $h_t > 0$, must cover various expenses. Here, w_t represents the wage rate per unit of labor at time t , so that the total income for an adult with human capital h_t is given by $w_t h_t$. This income must cover consumption in adulthood, $c_{1,t}$; savings $s_t \geq 0$; and the expenses associated with raising and educating children, which depend on the number of children $n_t > 0$. These costs include a fixed portion, $z \in (0, 1)$, of the adult's income dedicated to child-rearing, as well as an educational expenditure per child, $e_t \geq 0$. Thus, the budget constraint during adulthood is expressed as

$$c_{1,t} + s_t + n_t(e_t + z w_t h_t) = w_t h_t. \tag{3}$$

During retirement, old agents fund their consumption, $c_{2,t+1}$, using the returns from their previous savings. This relationship is captured by

$$c_{2,t+1} = r_{t+1}s_t, \quad (4)$$

where r_{t+1} is the interest factor at time $t + 1$, and, again, s_t represents the accumulated savings from adulthood.

The education of children depends on three factors: parental investment in formal education, the time grandparents allocate to teaching grandchildren, and the overall human capital in society. Specifically, we assume that the contribution of grandparents and parents to the formation of children's human capital are perfect substitutes. In fact, the production function of human capital is given by:

$$h_{t+1} = \pi \left(h_{t-1} \frac{\mu_t}{n_t} + \phi e_t \right)^\delta \bar{h}_t^{1-\delta}, \quad (5)$$

where $\pi > 0$ and $\phi > 0$ are parameters influencing the effectiveness of grandparent time and educational investment, $\delta \in (0, 1)$ reflects the role of grandparents and parents in human capital accumulation, and $\bar{h}_t > 0$ represents the average human capital in society.

Finally, given the definitions of μ_{t+1} as the time fraction devoted to educating grandchildren and l_{t+1} as the time allocated to leisure, we must have:

$$\mu_{t+1} + l_{t+1} = 1. \quad (6)$$

To summarize, the overall model consists in maximizing the utility function (2) under the aforementioned constraints, i.e.: (3)-(6), plus a non-negativity constraint on e_t , namely:

$$\max U_t(c_{1,t}, c_{2,t+1}, \mu_{t+1}, l_{t+1}, e_t, n_t) = \ln c_{1,t} + \rho \ln c_{2,t+1} + \theta \ln l_{t+1} + \frac{h_t}{h_{t-1}} \ln \mu_{t+1} + \beta \ln h_{t+1} + \lambda \ln n_t \quad (7)$$

subject to:

$$c_{1,t} + s_t + n_t(e_t + zw_t h_t) = w_t h_t \quad (8)$$

$$c_{2,t+1} = r_{t+1}s_t \quad (9)$$

$$h_{t+1} = \pi \left(h_{t-1} \frac{\mu_t}{n_t} + \phi e_t \right)^\delta \bar{h}_t^{1-\delta} \quad (10)$$

$$\mu_{t+1} + l_{t+1} = 1 \quad (11)$$

$$e_t \geq 0. \quad (12)$$

We also assume the existence of numerous competitive producers using a production technology with constant returns to scale, where capital fully depreciates after one period. In the OLG framework, this means that the depreciation rate of capital is set to 1, since each period corresponds to a generation lasting about 20-30 years, making it realistic to assume complete depreciation after one period (as in [4]). Therefore, the capital stock in a given period equals the savings accumulated in the previous period.

At time t , production relies on physical capital K_t and labor L_t . The total output Q_t is determined by the following Cobb-Douglas production function:

$$Q_t = F(K_t, L_t) = AK_t^\alpha L_t^{1-\alpha}, \quad (13)$$

where $A > 0$ represents total factor productivity, and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is the capital's contribution to output. Firms maximize profits $Q_t - w_t L_t - r_t K_t$, leading to the following conditions for wages and capital returns:

$$w_t = A(1 - \alpha) \frac{K_t^\alpha}{L_t^\alpha} \quad (14)$$

$$r_t = A\alpha \frac{K_t^{\alpha-1}}{L_t^\alpha}. \quad (15)$$

Following Hirazawa and Yakita [4], labor is defined as $L_t = h_t N_t$, and introducing $k_t = \frac{K_t}{N_t}$, we derive the following expressions for wages and returns:

$$w_t = A(1 - \alpha) \frac{k_t^\alpha}{h_t^\alpha} \quad (16)$$

$$r_t = A\alpha \frac{k_t^{\alpha-1}}{h_t^{\alpha-1}}. \quad (17)$$

Thus, assuming $K_{t+1} = s_t N_t$ and $N_{t+1} = n_t N_t$, we obtain:

$$k_{t+1} = \frac{K_{t+1}}{N_{t+1}} = \frac{s_t}{n_t}. \quad (18)$$

This formula also appears in [4].

Finally, as assumed by Kitaura and Yakita [5], under the condition that all agents within a generation are identical, we have that $\bar{h}_t = h_t$.

3. Solution of the examined problem

The proposed model is a constrained optimization model, as we aim to maximize the utility function (7) subject to the equality constraints (8)-(11) and the inequality constraint (12). If s_t is derived from (9), l_{t+1} from (11), and these are substituted along with the expression for h_{t+1} , a new reformulation of the model is obtained with a single equality constraint and one inequality constraint. This reformulation can be solved using the method of Lagrange multipliers: by associating a Lagrange multiplier with each constraint, the Lagrangian function associated with the new model can be constructed. It is easy to verify that for this model, the conditions of the Lagrange multiplier theorem are satisfied. Therefore, by setting the gradient of the Lagrangian function with respect to the decision variables $c_{1,t}$, $c_{2,t+1}$, μ_{t+1} , e_t , and n_t equal to zero and accounting for both the equality constraint and the complementary slackness conditions due to the inequality constraint, two systems are obtained, each of which holds in two regions of the set of solutions. This approach provides the so-called first-order conditions. These are necessary conditions within which to search for a local maximum. To also obtain sufficient conditions, it is necessary to impose that the Hessian matrix of the Lagrangian function is negative definite on the constraint set of the active constraints. Taking all these considerations into account, we obtain the aforementioned two regions, which are characterized, in addition to the inequality $\lambda - \beta\delta > 0$, by the following constraints:

$$\text{Region A: } \frac{w_t h_t}{\mu_t h_{t-1}} > \frac{1+\rho+\lambda-\beta\delta}{\beta\delta\phi}$$

$$\text{Region B: } \frac{w_t h_t}{\mu_t h_{t-1}} \leq \frac{1+\rho+\lambda-\beta\delta}{\beta\delta\phi}.$$

In region A, it holds that:

$$c_{1,t} = \frac{1}{1+\rho+\lambda-\beta\delta} \cdot \frac{h_{t-1}\mu_t + \phi w_t h_t}{\phi} \quad (19)$$

$$c_{2,t+1} = \frac{\rho}{1+\rho+\lambda-\beta\delta} \cdot \frac{h_{t-1}\mu_t + \phi w_t h_t}{\phi} r_{t+1} \quad (20)$$

$$s_t = \frac{\rho}{1+\rho+\lambda} \cdot \frac{h_{t-1}\mu_t + \phi w_t h_t}{\phi} \quad (21)$$

$$e_t = zw_t h_t \left(\frac{\beta\delta}{\lambda-\beta\delta} - \frac{1+\rho+\lambda}{\lambda-\beta\delta} \cdot \frac{h_{t-1}\mu_t}{h_{t-1}\mu_t + \phi w_t h_t} \right) \quad (22)$$

$$n_t = \frac{\lambda-\beta\delta}{1+\rho+\lambda} \cdot \frac{1}{zw_t h_t} \cdot \frac{h_{t-1}\mu_t + \phi w_t h_t}{\phi}, \quad (23)$$

while in region B, it holds that:

$$c_{1,t} = \frac{1}{1+\rho+\lambda-\beta\delta} w_t h_t \quad (24)$$

$$c_{2,t+1} = \frac{\rho}{1+\rho+\lambda-\beta\delta} w_t h_t r_{t+1} \quad (25)$$

$$s_t = \frac{\rho}{1+\rho+\lambda-\beta\delta} w_t h_t \quad (26)$$

$$e_t = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$n_t = \frac{\lambda - \beta\delta}{1 + \rho + \lambda - \beta\delta} \cdot \frac{1}{z} \tag{28}$$

Furthermore, in both regions it holds that:

$$\mu_{t+1} = \frac{h_t}{h_t + \theta h_{t-1}} \tag{29}$$

4. Results and discussion

We focus only on region A for the remainder of this work, leaving region B for future study.

If we substitute the values of s_t and n_t from the first-order conditions into (18), we obtain the following equation:

$$k_{t+1} = \frac{\rho}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z w_t h_t \tag{30}$$

Taking (30), (29) and (10) into account, and after appropriate substitutions, including (16), we obtain the following 3D discrete-time dynamic system:

$$T_A: \begin{cases} k_{t+1} = \frac{\rho}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z A(1 - \alpha) k_t^\alpha h_t^{1-\alpha} & (31) \\ \mu_{t+1} = \frac{h_t}{h_t + \theta h_{t-1}} & (32) \\ h_{t+1} = \pi \left[\frac{\beta\delta}{\lambda - \beta\delta} \phi z A(1 - \alpha) k_t^\alpha h_t^{1-\alpha} \right]^\delta h_t^{1-\delta}, & (33) \end{cases}$$

Where we have also exploited the assumption $\bar{h}_t = h_t$.

As in the works [1,6,7], it is useful to introduce the following variables: $x_t = \frac{k_t}{h_t}$ and $y_t = \frac{h_t}{h_{t-1}}$, which respectively represent the physical capital/human capital ratio and the human capital growth rate.

With the second-order condition $\lambda - \beta\delta > 0$ in mind, and using these substitutions, we can redefine region A as follows:

$$A(1 - \alpha) \frac{x_t^\alpha y_t}{\mu_t} > \frac{1 + \rho + \lambda - \beta\delta}{\beta\delta\phi} \tag{34}$$

Additionally, we can reformulate the system T_A as follows:

$$S_A: \begin{cases} x_{t+1} = \frac{\rho}{\pi\beta\delta\phi} \left[\frac{\beta\delta\phi}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z A(1 - \alpha) x_t^\alpha \right]^{1-\delta} & (35) \\ \mu_{t+1} = \frac{y_t}{y_t + \theta} & (36) \\ y_{t+1} = \pi \left[\frac{\beta\delta\phi}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z A(1 - \alpha) x_t^\alpha \right]^\delta & (37) \end{cases}$$

We observe that the nature of the system S_A is completely determined by equation (35). In fact, (37) is given by a constant multiplied by $x_t^{\alpha\delta}$, so if x_t converges, then y_t also converges. Conversely, if x_t diverges, then y_t also diverges. Furthermore, for (36), if y_t diverges, then μ_t converges to 1. Conversely, if y_t converges, then μ_t also converges. In both cases, μ_t converges. Based on the considerations just made, it is therefore sufficient to study the difference equation (35). In Proposition 1, we present the equilibrium points of (35) along with their stability.

Proposition 1. *The difference equation (35) has two equilibrium points: the origin, which is unstable, and the point*

$$x^* = \left\{ \frac{\rho}{\pi\beta\delta\phi} \left[\frac{\beta\delta\phi}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z A(1 - \alpha) \right]^{1-\delta} \right\}^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha(1-\delta)}}, \tag{38}$$

which is asymptotically stable.

Proof. Let $f(x_t) := \frac{\rho}{\pi\beta\delta\phi} \left[\frac{\beta\delta\phi}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z A(1 - \alpha) x_t^\alpha \right]^{1-\delta}$. Then, the equation $x = f(x)$ is clearly satisfied by $x = 0$, so the origin is an equilibrium point of the difference equation (35). Now, assuming $x \neq 0$, by dividing both sides of the equation $x = f(x)$ by x , we obtain

$$x^{1-\alpha(1-\delta)} = \frac{\rho}{\pi\beta\delta\phi} \left[\frac{\beta\delta\phi}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z A(1 - \alpha) \right]^{1-\delta} \tag{39}$$

Raising both sides of (39) to the power of $\frac{1}{1-\alpha(1-\delta)}$, we obtain (38). As for the stability of the equilibrium points found, we need to know the first derivative (with respect to x_t) of the function f . It is given by:

$$f'(x_t) = \frac{\rho}{\pi\beta\delta\phi} \left[\frac{\beta\delta\phi}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z A(1 - \alpha) \right]^{1-\delta} \alpha(1 - \delta) x_t^{\alpha(1-\delta)-1} \tag{40}$$

Since α and δ are between 0 and 1, the exponent of x_t in (40) is negative, and thus the first derivative of f is not defined for $x_t = 0$. For the same reason, it is clear that $\lim_{x_t \rightarrow 0^+} f'(x_t) = +\infty$ and thus the origin is an unstable equilibrium point. As for the equilibrium point x^* , it is easy to verify that $f'(x^*) = \alpha(1 - \delta)$. Since α and δ are between 0 and 1, their product is also between 0 and 1, and thus x^* is an asymptotically stable equilibrium point. ■

We would like to make an important observation following the results just proven. In fact, what was proven in Proposition 1 does not take into account region A, which in the new variables x_t and y_t is described by (34). We observe that if $x_t = 0$, then from (37) we also have $y_t = 0$, and thus (34) cannot be satisfied. Therefore, we can exclude the origin as an equilibrium point in region A. At this point, it is legitimate to ask whether the equilibrium point x^* also exists in region A. Proposition 2 provides an answer to this question.

Proposition 2. *There exists a combination of parameters such that the equilibrium point x^* belongs to region A.*

Proof. From (35)-(38), we have that the coordinates of the three-dimensional equilibrium point of the system S_A are given by x^* , by $y^* = \pi \left[\frac{\beta\delta\phi}{\lambda - \beta\delta} z A(1 - \alpha) \right]^\delta (x^*)^{\alpha\delta}$ and by $\mu^* = \frac{y^*}{y^* + \theta}$. Therefore, the inequality (34) evaluated at x^* , y^* , and μ^* can be rewritten as

$$A(1 - \alpha) (x^*)^\alpha (y^* + \theta) > \frac{1 + \rho + \lambda - \beta\delta}{\beta\delta\phi} \tag{41}$$

Since x^* and y^* increase as A increases, it is evident that, given the parameters on the right-hand side of (41), there exists a sufficiently large value of A that satisfies (41). ■

To confirm what has been proven, we want to provide a numerical example starting from the following combination of parameters: $\alpha = 0.5$, $A = 10$, $\beta = 0.9$, $\delta = 0.9$, $\lambda = 0.9$, $z = 0.9$, $\phi = 0.5$, $\pi = 0.2$, $\rho = 0.2$, and $\theta = 0.8$. Let's begin by verifying that the equilibrium point inside region A exists. In fact, approximating to four decimal places, we find: $x^* = 3.5541$, $y^* = 5.3044$, and $\mu^* = 0.8689$. Substituting these values into (41), this inequality is satisfied.

With this parameter configuration, the map associated with (35) is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 The map of the difference equation (35) with the proposed parameter configuration.

As we mentioned, the origin is not part of region A, but if we only consider the difference equation (35), Fig. 1 provides clear graphical evidence that the origin is an unstable equilibrium point, since, as already proven in Proposition 1, the slope of the tangent line to the map at the origin tends to $+\infty$.

From Fig. 1, we can clearly observe that the slope of the tangent line at the interior fixed point is between 0 and 1, and thus this fixed point is asymptotically stable. Based on the reasoning in Proposition 1, and on the fact that the origin does not belong to region A, this fixed point is also globally asymptotically stable in region A.

In Fig. 2-4, we respectively show the evolution of x_t , μ_t , and y_t respectively, with the aforementioned parameter configuration, choosing $x_0 = 4$, $\mu_0 = 0.5$, and $y_0 = 6$. As clearly seen in Fig. 2 and in line with what was proven in Proposition 1, the orbit converges to the point $x^* = 3.5541$ after a few iterations. Furthermore, from Figure 3 it is evident that μ_t converges to $\mu^* = 0.8689$. Therefore, there is an equilibrium level of time allocation to which μ_t converges. Finally, from Figure 4 it can be observed that y_t converges to $y^* = 5.3044$.

Fig. 2 The evolution of x_t with the proposed parameter configuration and the initial points considered.

Fig. 3 The evolution of μ_t with the proposed parameter configuration and the initial points considered.

Fig. 4 The evolution of y_t with the proposed parameter configuration and the initial points considered.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the growing significance of grandparents in the educational development of their grandchildren, driven by the increasing longevity of the population. As life expectancy rises, grandparents are more likely to form lasting relationships with their grandchildren, creating additional opportunities to influence their educational outcomes. This work is a natural evolution of Baldi et al. [1], where the time grandparents dedicate to their grandchildren's education was treated as a fixed parameter. In contrast, we consider this time as a variable, determined by the trade-off between leisure and the desire to contribute to their grandchildren's upbringing.

The model we developed provides new insights into how such contributions can affect the transmission of education over time, offering important implications for long-term social and economic outcomes.

Encouraged by the promising results, we plan to continue with this line of research. Possible developments include a different evolution of h_{t+1} or a scenario where grandparents dedicate their time to work with reduced productivity.

Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU under the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR) National Innovation Ecosystem grant ECS00000041 - VITALITY - CUP D83C22000710005.

6. References

1. M. M. Baldi, R. Coppier, E. Michetti, *Mathematical Social Sciences*, 131, 67-79 (2024)
2. G. S. Becker, N. Tomes, *Human capital and the rise and fall of families*, 4 (3, part 2), S1-S39 (1986)
3. T. Bol, M. Kalmijn, *Grandparents' resources and grandchildren's schooling: Does grandparental involvement moderate the grandparent effect?*, *Social Science Research*, 55, 155-170 (2016)
4. M. Hirazawa, A. Yakita, *Labor supply of elderly people, fertility, and economic development*, *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 51, 75-96 (2017)
5. K. Kitaura, A. Yakita, *Labor supply of elderly people, fertility, and economic development*, *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 51, 75-96 (2017)
6. A. Yakita, *Human capital accumulation, fertility and economic development*, *Journal of Economics*, 99, 97-116 (2010)
7. K. Kitaura, A. Yakita, *School education, learning-by-doing, and fertility in economic development*, *Review of Development Economics*, 14, 736-749 (2010)